

AI Acelerator for a Core RISC-V

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Abstract

Neural networks rely heavily on multiplication operations for weight calculations, which are computationally expensive in terms of power consumption and execution time. This report presents the implementation of a Logarithmic Number System (LNS) arithmetic unit for a RISC-V core that addresses these challenges. In LNS representation, multiplication and division become simple addition and subtraction operations, while square root reduces to a single bit shift. The main contribution is a novel approach to approximating LNS addition and subtraction using linear splines with a greedy algorithm that minimizes lookup table memory requirements. We developed a 16-bit LNS format (1 sign bit, 8 integer bits, 7 fractional bits) and implemented an LNS Unit (LNSU) achieving a maximum 1-bit approximation error with only 324 bytes of memory. The design synthesizes at 125 MHz on FPGA with a throughput of one operation per clock cycle and single-cycle latency, using 2256 LUTs, 629 flip-flops, and 2 DSPs. This work demonstrates that LNS can provide IEEE-754 floating-point equivalent precision for neural network weight representations while significantly reducing hardware complexity and power consumption for multiplication-intensive operations.

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List of Acronyms

NN	Neural Network
FP	Floating Point
LNS	Logarithmic Number System
LNSU	Logarithmic Number System Unit
LUT	Look Up Table
DSP	Digital Signal Processing block/unit

1 Introduction

Neural networks are a model that are present in most of AI algorithms today. Their performance and precision is crucial to guarantee successful predictions. For that reason, an implementation of an accelerator into a CPU core would make this process as fast as possible and, with the right format, highly precise. In this report, we discuss the implementation of the Logarithmic Number System (LNS) in custom instructions of the RISC-V architecture as well as a new unit designed for this system, LNSU, to hold values of NNs' weights.

1.1 Context

This project was conducted at INESC TEC and in the Department of Electronics in the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto. INESC TEC is a private non-profit organization which conducts research and development in ITT&E fields.

Our internship arose from an idea shared in a talk given by Bill Dally from NVIDIA at Hot Chips 2023. The idea comes from the need to represent data with high precision, performance and low usage of power. The system mentioned was the LNS - it is able to represent various values in the interval $(0, 1]$ (main domain of the weight values) with high precision as IEEE-754 floating point counter part and it also turns multiplication, division and square root into much faster operations (addition, subtraction and right shift).

1.2 Problem

Current NNs rely on the IEEE-754 floating point representation to hold weight values and perform calculations. NNs require lots of multiplication operations which are very expensive in terms of power usage and time.

1.3 Objectives & Results

1. Find a format for LNS such that it gives a precision as good as FP
2. Approximate precisely the addition and subtraction of 2 numbers in LNS format
3. Develop a LNSU embedded into a RISC-V Core

2 Theory

This chapter describes the work undertaken to achieve the expected results.

2.1 LNS

The Logarithmic Number System consists of prepending the sign of a number to the logarithmic of its absolute value. This way, we can also represent negative values with this system with a special case for the value 0.

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_x &= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x < 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } x \geq 0 \end{cases} \\
 L_x &= \log_2(|x|) \\
 x &= (-1)^{S_x} \cdot 2^{L_x}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

L_x is a 2's complement fixed point number. Thus, the interval from $(0, 1)$ is represented by values of L_x which are negative and $(1, \infty)$ by positive ones.

The main LNS format that we chose to approach during this project was the following, although we also tested the precision of other formats:

S_x	L_x Integer Part	L_x Fractional Part
1 bit	8 bits	7 bits

Table 1: Chosen LNS Format for 16 bits

In this format, the lowest value of L_x is -128 or $0x4000$ which we can define as $-\infty$ for the purpose of simplification. Therefore, when we convert this value to a float, we see that $2^{-128} = 0$. On the other hand, the largest value of L_x is approximately 128 or ≈ 127.999 and so can denote this value $0x3FFF$ has $+\infty$, as it is the largest value we can represent, giving as also $2^{\approx 128} = +\infty$ or $0xCFFF$ which gives $-2^{\approx 128} = -\infty$ (here the difference is given by S_x being equal to 0 or 1).

The operations we chose to tackle are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 z = x + y &\Leftrightarrow L_z = \log_2(2^{L_x} + 2^{L_y}) \\
 z = x - y &\Leftrightarrow L_z = \log_2(2^{L_x} - 2^{L_y}) \\
 z = x \cdot y &\Leftrightarrow L_z = \log_2(2^{L_x} \cdot 2^{L_y}) = L_x + L_y \\
 z = \frac{x}{y} &\Leftrightarrow L_z = \log_2\left(\frac{2^{L_x}}{2^{L_y}}\right) = L_x - L_y \\
 z = \sqrt{x} &\Leftrightarrow L_z = \log_2\left(\sqrt{2^{L_x}}\right) = \frac{L_x}{2} = L_x \ggg 1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The implementation for multiplication, division and square root then become trivial operations in LNS format. Multiplication becomes an addition of two fixed point numbers, which is just an addition of two integers, division becomes a subtraction similar to the previous and the square root is just a division by 2 or better saying a shift right logical.

The problem here is to calculate the results for the addition and subtraction. This operation becomes a non-trivial operation with arithmetic functions. The common approach in various papers is to approximate these functions with a Taylor Series term and error correction terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f^- &: (-\infty, 0) \rightarrow (-\infty, 0) \\
 x &\rightarrow \log_2(1 - 2^x) \\
 f^+ &: (-\infty, 0) \rightarrow (0, 1) \\
 x &\rightarrow \log_2(1 + 2^x)
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

This is derived from:

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_z &= \log_2(x \pm y) \\
 &= \log_2\left(|x| \cdot \left|1 \pm \frac{y}{x}\right|\right) \\
 &= \log_2(|x|) + \log_2\left(\left|1 \pm \frac{y}{x}\right|\right) \\
 &= L_x + \log_2(1 \pm 2^{L_y - L_x}), \quad |x| \geq |y|
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The condition $|x| \geq |y|$ guarantees that $L_x \geq L_y$ and so $L_y - L_x \leq 0$. If $L_y - L_x = 0$ then we either have an addition or a singularity (addition or subtraction operations, respectively), but we'll handle that later.

Papers like the references describe the methods of approximating this function with a Taylor Series and a hardware implementation. However, we found that this approach would require LUTs which would not be at all feasible for us as the number of rows for each table increases exponentially with the number of precise bits. We decided, then, to try a simpler approach and approximate these functions with linear splines.

Splines are step functions with polynomial functions at each step with at most degree m given the degree of the spline. Linear splines are then the special case where $m = 1$. In order to construct a spline, we need n (x_i, f_i) points giving us $n - 1$ intervals. The formula for a linear spline, LS, is:

$$\text{LS}(x) = \begin{cases} (x_1 - x)\frac{f_0}{h_1} + (x - x_0)\frac{f_1}{h_1}, & \text{if } x_0 \leq x \leq x_1 \\ \vdots \\ (x_i - x)\frac{f_{i-1}}{h_i} + (x - x_{i-1})\frac{f_i}{h_i}, & \text{if } x_{i-1} \leq x \leq x_i, \text{ with } h_i = x_i - x_{i-1} \\ \vdots \\ (x_n - x)\frac{f_{n-1}}{h_n} + (x - x_{n-1})\frac{f_n}{h_n}, & \text{if } x_{n-1} \leq x \leq x_n \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

The upper bound of the error associated with this approximation is given by:

$$\varepsilon \leq \frac{1}{8} \max_{x \in [a, b]} \left(\left| \frac{d^2}{dx^2} f(x) \right| h^2 \right), \quad h = \max \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n h_i \right) \tag{6}$$

If we want to minimize the error at each step we can think of them as a single spline at each interval we want to approximate.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} f(x) &= \frac{d^2}{dx^2} \log_2(1 \pm 2^x) \\
 &= \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1}{(1 \pm 2^x) \ln(2)} \frac{d}{dx} (1 \pm 2^x) \right) \\
 &= \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\pm 2^x \ln(2)}{(1 \pm 2^x) \ln(2)} \right) \\
 &= \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\pm 2^x}{1 \pm 2^x} \right) \\
 &= \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1 \pm 2^x - 1}{1 \pm 2^x} \right) \\
 &= \frac{d}{dx} \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 \pm 2^x} \right) \\
 &= -\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1}{1 \pm 2^x} \right) \\
 &= -\frac{-1}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} \frac{d}{dx} (1 \pm 2^x) \\
 &= \pm \ln(2) \frac{2^x}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

To study the maximum of the second derivative, we can see its critical points by taking its derivative as well.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{d}{dx} \left(\pm \ln(2) \frac{2^x}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} \right) &= \pm \ln(2) \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{2^x}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} \right) \\
 &= \pm \ln(2) \left(\frac{d}{dx} (2^x) \cdot \frac{1}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} + 2^x \frac{d}{dx} ((1 \pm 2^x)^{-2}) \right) \\
 &= \pm \ln(2) \left(\frac{\ln(2) 2^x}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} - 2 \cdot 2^x (1 \pm 2^x)^{-3} \frac{d}{dx} (1 \pm 2^x) \right) \\
 &= \pm \ln(2) \left(\frac{\ln(2) 2^x}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} - 2 \cdot 2^x (1 \pm 2^x)^{-3} \cdot (\pm \ln(2) 2^x) \right) \\
 &= \frac{\pm \ln^2(2) 2^x}{(1 \pm 2^x)^2} \left(1 \mp \frac{2^{x+1}}{1 \pm 2^x} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Continuing with the critical point analysis and subsequent tables...

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^-} \frac{\ln^2(2) 2^x}{(1 + 2^x)^2} \left(1 - \frac{2^{x+1}}{1 + 2^x} \right) &= \frac{\ln^2(2) 2^{0^-}}{(1 + 2^{0^-})^2} \left(1 - \frac{2^{0^-+1}}{1 + 2^{0^-}} \right) \\
 &= \frac{\ln^2(2)}{(1 + 1)^2} \left(1 - \frac{2}{1 + 1} \right) \\
 &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{x \rightarrow 0^-} \frac{-\ln^2(2)2^x}{(1-2^x)^2} \left(1 - \frac{2^{x+1}}{1-2^x}\right) &= \frac{-\ln^2(2)2^x}{(1-2^{0^-})^2} \left(1 - \frac{2^{0^-+1}}{1-2^{0^-}}\right) \\
 &= \frac{-\ln^2(2)2^x}{0^+} \left(1 - \frac{2}{0^+}\right) \\
 &= \infty \cdot (-\infty) \\
 &= -\infty
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

	$-\infty$	$x \in (-\infty, 0)$	0
$(f^+)''(x)$	0	\nearrow	$\frac{\ln(2)}{4}$
$(f^+)'''(x)$	0	+	0

Table 2: Analysis of the second and third derivative of the add function

	$-\infty$	$x \in (-\infty, 0)$	0
$(f^-)''(x)$	0	\searrow	$-\infty$
$(f^-)'''(x)$	0	-	$-\infty$

Table 3: Analysis of the second and third derivative of the subtract function

Therefore, as the expression for the upper bound of the error includes the maximum of the absolute value of the second derivative $\left(\frac{1}{8} \max_{x \in [a,b]} (|f''(x)|h^2)\right)$ and, in both cases, it is always increasing, the upper bound of the error is determined by the extreme of the interval b . Hence, the error for each step for a spline of $n + 1 \cup_{i=0}^n \{(x_i, f_i)\}$ points is equal to (h is constant as for each step there is only one interval):

$$\varepsilon_i \leq \frac{\ln(2) \cdot 2^{x_i} \cdot h_i^2}{8(1 \pm 2^{x_i})^2}, \quad h_i = x_i - x_{i-1}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \tag{11}$$

2.2 Solution

With this formula, we decided to create the respective splines with a greedy approach. We start with the end points ($-\infty$ and 0) and while the number of intervals is less than a fixed value k , we add another point to the set. The criteria is to choose the interval with the maximum error and add a new point in the middle.

```

spline.cpp
1 double err(const double b, const double h, const int8_t sign) {
2   double numerator = std::pow(h, 2) * std::pow(2.0, b);
3   double denominator = std::pow(1.0 + std::pow(-1.0, sign) * std::pow(2.0, b), 2);
4   return numerator / denominator;
5 }
    
```

Figure 1: Error function of the Splines (Constant terms are ignored for the comparison)

```

● ● ● spline.cpp
1 double add_func(const double diff) {
2   return std::log2(1.0 + std::exp2(diff));
3 }
4
5 double sub_func(const double diff) {
6   return std::log2(1.0 - std::exp2(diff));
7 }

```

Figure 2: Add and Subtraction Functions

```

● ● ● spline.cpp
1 int16_t calculate_xmb(const std::vector<Point>& table, const int16_t x, const int16_t s_table, const int16_t precision) {
2   int16_t i = 0;
3   for (; x > table[i].x && i < s_table; i++);
4   return (((int32_t)table[i].m * (int32_t)x) >> precision) + table[i].b;
5 }
6
7 int16_t calculate_xf(const std::vector<Point>& table, const int16_t x, const int16_t s_table) {
8   int16_t i = 0;
9   for (; x > table[i].x && i < s_table; i++);
10  if (i == 0)
11    return 0;
12
13  const int16_t h = table[i].x - table[i - 1].x;
14  const int16_t log2_h = log2_int(h);
15
16  const int32_t
17  a = ((int32_t)(x - table[i - 1].x)) * table[i].y, // Q1.M * Q1.M = Q2I.2M
18  b = ((int32_t)(table[i].x - x)) * table[i - 1].y, // Q1.M * Q1.M = Q2I.2M
19  c = (a + b) >> log2_h; // Q2I.2M >> log2_h = Q(2I + M).M
20
21  return (int16_t)c;
22 }

```

Figure 3: Add and Subtraction Approximation Functions

```

1 void greedy_spline(
2     std::vector<Point>& table, size_t s_table,
3     const int8_t sign, const int16_t precision
4 ) {
5     const int16_t
6     add_start = ~(1 << (3 + precision)) + 1, // -8 at any precision, we take the complement of it
7     sub_start = ~(1 << (3 + precision)),     // -8 - 2^precision, we take the complement and subtract one (which is just taking the ~)
8     add_end   = 0,                          // 0
9     sub_end   = 1;                          // -2^precision
10
11     std::vector<int16_t> hs;
12     std::vector<double> error;
13
14     table.push_back({(int16_t)(sign ? sub_start : add_start), 0, 0, 0});
15     table.push_back({(int16_t)(sign ? sub_end : add_end), 0, 0, 0});
16
17     for (size_t i = 0; i < s_table - 2; i++) {
18         for (size_t j = 0; j < table.size() - 1; j++) {
19             hs.push_back(table[j + 1].x - table[j].x);
20             error.push_back(err(QI_M_to_double(table[j].x, precision), QI_M_to_double(hs[j], precision), sign));
21         }
22
23         size_t max_index = 0;
24         for (size_t j = 1; j < hs.size(); j++)
25             if ((error[j] > error[max_index]) && (hs[j] > 1))
26                 max_index = j;
27
28         table.insert(
29             table.begin() + max_index + 1,
30             {static_cast<int16_t>(table[max_index].x + (hs[max_index] >> 1)), 0, 0, 0}
31         );
32
33         hs.clear();
34         error.clear();
35     }
36
37     for (size_t i = 0; i < s_table; i++)
38         table[i].y = double_to_QI_M(
39             sign == 1 ?
40             (sub_func(QI_M_to_double(table[i].x, precision)))
41             : (add_func(QI_M_to_double(table[i].x, precision))),
42             precision
43         );
44
45     for (size_t i = 1; i < s_table; i++) {
46         int32_t temp = static_cast<int32_t>(table[i].y) - static_cast<int32_t>(table[i - 1].y);
47         temp <= precision;
48         temp >= log2_int(table[i].x - table[i - 1].x);
49         table[i].m = static_cast<int16_t>(temp);
50         table[i].b = table[i].y - ((table[i].m * table[i].x) >> precision);
51     }
52 }

```

Figure 4: Greedy generator of the Splines

In this function, we are representing the points in fixed point integers values of $k - 1$ digits (the format labeled in Table 1 - without the bit sign, we can calculate the spline for any precisions in 16 and 8 bit LNS with some restrictions, given that the values between -8 and 0 have to be included). The minimum interval length we allow to create another point in the middle is 2 or $2 \cdot 2^{-\text{precision}}$ (loop from lines 23 to 26).

Allow us to provide a brief recapitulation as there is something important about the spline step formula Equation 5 that was not yet addressed. Initially, we just went with the formula given by the text books and did not think much about it. It was relatively simple and straight forward, not to complicated in terms of the application of the hardware - two subtractions, two divisions by a power of 2 (every new point was introduced in the middle of the parent interval and the starting interval was a power of 2) which turn into shift operations, two multiplications and a final addition. In total, we would have 4 operations, because the pairs of operations can run in parallel except for the final sum. This is also great in terms of memory as we only need to store two columns, a list of x_i 's and a list of f_i 's that gives memory = $2 \cdot (n + 1) \cdot 2$ bytes = $4 \cdot (n + 1)$ bytes where $n + 1$ is the number of points (x_i, f_i) . However, we can also write Equation 5 as

$$LS_i(x) = \frac{f_i - f_{i-1}}{h_i} \cdot x + \frac{f_{i-1}x_i - f_i x_{i-1}}{h_i} = m_i \cdot x + b_i, \quad h_i = x_i - x_{i-1}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (12)$$

This approach (which we'll call XMB and the other XF) minimizes even further the operations the LNSU as to do in terms of computation. In spite of that, now the memory grows as

memory = $3 \cdot (n + 1) \cdot 2$ bytes = $6 \cdot (n + 1)$ bytes as we still need the list of x_i 's in order to find the interval x is in. This is also being calculated in the greedy spline function in Figure 4 in the loop from lines 45 to 51.

For this very reason, we decided to evaluate the performance and precisions of both of this approaches.

3 Results

3.1 Implementation

The LNSU has three main components, the square root, the adder/subtractor and the multiplier/divisor.

As said before, the square root is a simple shift right of one, and the multiplier/divider becomes an adder/subtractor of two integers with a XOR to the result signal.

The main challenge was the implementation of the adder/subtractor. First of all, the assembly operation can be different for a given exponent operation. For example, a subtraction of a positive number with a negative one becomes an addition of exponents. This is because the formula to calculate the result exponent is independent of the signal, so we need to abstract the sign for this operation. On Table 4 we have the operation performed in each case of operands signal and the resulting operation. The difference between the addition and subtraction of exponents is only the lookup table to use.

Op1 signal	Op2 signal	Addition	Subtraction
neg	neg	exp add	exp sub
neg	pos	exp sub	exp add
pos	neg	exp sub	exp add
pos	pos	exp add	exp sub

Table 4: Exponent operation in each case of operands signals and exponent operation

At the same time we calculate the absolute difference of the exponents.

With the lookup table defined and the absolute difference of exponents, we determine the spline needed and compute the resulting exponent with a multiply-add.

The result's sign corresponds to the sign of the first operand when the exponents are added.

When the exponents are subtracted, the situation becomes more complex. If the first operand has the greater magnitude, the result's sign equals that of the first operand. If the second operand has the greater magnitude, the result's sign is given by $S_{op2} \text{ XOR } (S_{op1} \text{ XNOR } S_{op2})$. In other words, if the second operand has a greater module, the result's sign will match the second operator's sign when the operands have different ones, or it will be inverted when the operands share the same sign.

3.2 Results

In order to evaluate the maximum error of the approximation, we decided to make scripts in C and C++ and the results are the following:

Figure 5: Error against table size in bytes

	Error (Bits)	Table Size (Rows)	Table Size (Bytes)
Addition XF	1	10	40
Addition XMB	1	12	72
Addition XMB	2	10	60
Subtraction XF	1	50	200
Subtraction XF	2	41	164
Subtraction XF	4	24	96
Subtraction XMB	1	42	252
Subtraction XMB	2	41	246
Subtraction XMB	4	20	120

Table 5: Spline Precision in Bits (Q8.7)

As expected, the addition spline behaves way better than the subtraction one in both XMB and XF since the subtraction function has a singularity when it approaches 0 and its first, second and third derivative approach negative infinity as well. Despite that, it is curious to note that the XMB table for addition needs more rows than the XF table to get an error of 1 bit at most. Although it is only 2 rows, the amount of memory needed is fairly more due to the fact this table grows as $6(n + 1)$ bytes instead of $4(n + 1)$.

The error of the XMB addition table has compared to the XF one might be due to the previous pre-calculation of the m_i and b_i values, which are themselves approximations and the expressions can be numerically unstable, and, on the other hand, in the case of subtraction, the XF expressions are probably more numerically unstable compared to the XMB counterpart as they need more rows to get the same precision. This, we will not verify since it does not make much difference.

Although the XF tables present less memory for the same error, that implementation was not synthesizable in one clock cycle, resulting in an incremented latency if implemented in two clock cycles or more. With this in mind, we developed the XMB tables.

Our final implementation, using this tables with a maximum of one bit error required a memory of 324 Bytes. With the remaining circuit our LNSU required 2256 LUTs, 629 FF and 2 DSPs. Our LNSU have a throughput of 1 results per clock cycle and a latency of one clock cycle up to 125 MHz on the FPGA (Pynq Z2 Xc7z20-1clg400-1).

4 Conclusion

We successfully developed a Arithmetic Unit for operands in the format LNS with a little amount of memory for the spline tables, that have an ideal performance in order to throughput and latency.

The approximation for the addition and subtraction operations present a maximum of one of error with the tables sizes chosen, but for the purpose of LNS this error is insignificant.

4.1 Future Work

For future work, the conversion of Integer to LNS, LNS to Integer, Float to LNS and LNS to Float should be implemented. This is not necessary if the input and output data of a program could be in LNS, but it could be useful.

Larger sizes of LNS and different exponents should be studied.

New circuits should be developed to try reduce the hardware unites required for the LNSU.

5 Bibliography

Bibliography